

Household Follow-up CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
Section 1: Exited Household members		
3	How many people have left the house?	One Two Three Four Five More than 5
<i>Please fill in Q3a-Q3cii for each exited participant</i>		
3a	Participant ID	
3b	How long ago did the participant leave the house?	DD/MM/YYYY
3c	Reason for moving / left house?	Visiting friends or family (go to Q4) Work (go to Q4) In hospital (go to Q4) Died
3ci	Date of death	DD/MM/YYYY
3cii	Cause of death	
Section 2: New Household members		
4	Are there any new members of the household?	Yes No
4a	How many new members?	One Two Three Four Five More than 5
4b	Participant ID	
<i>Please fill a baseline CRF for each new participant</i>		
Section 3: Visitors		
5	Have you had any NEW visitors sleeping in the house who do not normally stay?	Yes No (go to Q6)

5a	How many visitors?	One Two Three Four Five More than 5
<i>Please complete Q5b-Q5e for EACH visitor</i>		
5b	What is their name?	
5c	What is their Gender	Male Female Prefer not to say
5d	What is their relationship to the family?	Household head Household family member Relative not from the household Friend Employee Other (specify)
5e	What is the age?	____ yrs
Section 4: New Animals or changes to Animal Practices		
6	Have you lost any of these individual animals from your household since our LAST VISIT?	Yes No (go to Q7)
6a	If so, which ones? <i>Tick all species that apply</i>	Cattle (beef) Cattle (dairy) Goat Sheep Pigs Chickens Equines Dogs Doves Guinea fowl Turkeys Ducks Cats Other (specify)
<i>For EACH animal lost complete Q6b-6d</i>		
6b	How many of these animals have you lost from your household? <i>Complete for each species animal</i>	
6c	Why do you no longer own these animals?	Sold (go to Q7) Eaten (go to Q7)

	<i>Complete for each animal species lost</i>	Missing (go to Q7) Given Away (go to Q7) Died
6d	Why did they die? <i>Complete for each animal species that died</i>	Respiratory illness / cough Digestive tract illness / diarrhoea Reproductive illness / abortion / stillbirth Sudden Death Skin disease / wounds External parasites Neurological signs Other (specify)
7	Do you own any new animals since your last visit?	Yes No (go to Q8)
7a	If so, which ones? Tick all species that apply	Cattle (beef) Cattle (dairy) Goat Sheep Pigs Chickens Equines Dogs Doves Guinea fowl Turkeys Ducks Cats Other (specify)
<i>For EACH new animal species lost complete Q7b</i>		
7b	How many of these animals have you gained into your household? Complete for each species of animal	
8	What animals are kept now in TOTAL?	Cattle (beef) Cattle (dairy) Goat Sheep Pigs Chickens Equines Dogs Doves Guinea fowl Turkeys Ducks Cats Other (specify)

		None (go to Q11)
	<i>For each animal species currently owned, complete Q8a-Q8d</i>	
8a	How many are owned? <i>Complete for each species of animal</i>	
8b	Where are the animals kept? <i>Complete for each species of animal</i>	In the house Shelter /Boma within household compound Shelter /Boma outside the household compound "Sometimes in the house, sometimes in the compound " Free roaming Zero Grazing Fenced individual farm grazing Communal Grazing Pastoral Free range Tethered Housed Other (specify)
8c	Have you changed what you do with your animal manure since our LAST VISIT? <i>Complete for each species of animal</i>	Yes No (go to Q8d)
8ci	What do you do now? <i>Complete for each species of animal</i>	Do nothing (i.e., leave where passed) Discard into environment Open air Used as fertilizer yourself Sold for cash Taken by other farmers or people Other
8d	Have you changed any of your feed products since your last visit? <i>Complete for each species of animal</i>	Yes No (go to Q9)
8di	What do you do now? <i>Complete for each species of animal</i>	Pasture Pasture /Scavenging Waste (household /restaurant etc) Grains / crop residues Feed mixed at farm Commercial / pre-mix feeds Other
Section 5: Animal health and antibiotic usage		

9	Has there been sickness in any of your animals since your LAST VISIT?	Yes No (go to Q10)
9a	Which animals have been sick? Tick all that apply	Cattle Goat Sheep Pigs Poultry Equines Other (specify)
<i>Complete Q9b-Q9div for each species of animal that was sick</i>		
9b	What kind of disease did they have?	Respiratory illness / cough Digestive tract illness / diarrhoea Reproductive illness / abortion / stillbirth Sudden Death Skin disease / wounds External parasites Neurological signs Other (specify)
9c	Was the disease diagnosed by yourself?	Yes No
9ci	If not you, then by whom was it diagnosed?	Traditional healer Farmer Herdsman Community animal health worker / assistant veterinary officer Private veterinarian Official (governmental) veterinarian Other (specify)
9d	What were the sick animals treated with?	Vaccines Anthelmintics (albendazole etc) Acaricides (ectoparasites) Tetracyclines Sulphonamides Penicillin (and combinations) Fluoroquinolones Macrolides Aminoglycosides Other antibiotics (specify) Vitamins/ iron supplements Other drugs (specify) Nothing (go to Q10)
9di	Where did you get these drugs from?	Private vet Public / official vet Animal health worker Veterinary drug store Human pharmacy

		Markets Feed providers Farmers Via NGOs Other (specify)
9dii	How long do you use this drug?	As advised Until animal(s) cured Until package empty As long as I can afford One-time treatment Continuously over extended period
9diii	Who administered it?	Household member Vet (or VAO) Other
9div	How was the drug applied/given?	Injection Oral With feed With water On Skin Other
10	Any other medications, drugs or vaccines given to your animals irrespective of illness since our LAST VISIT?	Yes No (go to Q11)
10a	Which Animals?	Cattle Goat Sheep Pigs Poultry Equines Other (specify)
<i>Complete 10b-Q10c for each species of animal that was given medication</i>		
10b	What did you give them?	Vaccines Anthelmintics (albendazole etc) Acaricides (ectoparasites) Tetracyclines Sulphonamides Penicillin (and combinations) Fluoroquinolones Macrolides Aminoglycosides Other antibiotics (specify) Vitamins/ iron supplements Other drugs (specify)
10c	Why did you give this drug to them?	Prevent the animals from becoming sick

		Cure sick animals and prevent them from becoming sick Fattening / increasing animal growth Other (specify)
	Section 6: Household experience of illness and antibiotics	
11	Is anyone in the house unwell at present or has been unwell since our LAST VISIT	Yes No (go to Q12)
11a	How many people have been unwell?	
	<i>For EACH unwell member, please fill in Q11b-Q11dii</i>	
11b	Enter the Participant ID.	
11c	What were they unwell with?	Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed) Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)
11c	Where did they go for care?	Tertiary referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend CHAM facility Self-treat with left over drugs Other (specify) Nowhere
11d	Did they get antibiotics?	Yes No (go to Q12)
11di	What antibiotics did they get? Fill in each antibiotic	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin

		Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxymethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown
11dii	What form was the antibiotic(s) Fill in for each antibiotic	Tablet Capsule Syrup Suspension Injection Don't Know
12	Have any members of the household other than yourself taken an antibiotic for any other reason since our LAST VISIT (not captured already)?	Yes No (go to Q13)
<i>For EACH member who took antibiotics, please fill in Q12a-Q12</i>		
12a	Enter the Participant ID	
12b	What antibiotics did they get? <i>Fill in each antibiotic</i>	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime

		Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxymethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown
12c	What form was the antibiotic(s) <i>Fill in for each antibiotic</i>	Tablet Capsule Syrup Suspension Injection Don't Know
12d	Where did they get the medication from?	Self-treat with left over drugs Referral Hospital (QECH) Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend CHAM facility Other (specify)
12e	How long did they take it for?	As advised Until cured Until package empty As long as I could afford to One-time treatment Continuously over extended period
13	You have completed data collection for this participant. Please thank them for their time.	

14	Staff signature	
15	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY